

ION-EXCHANGE REACTIONS WITH HETEROIONIC SYNTHETIC RESINS. PART I. CATION EXCHANGE

BY L. POCHHALI

Ion-exchange reactions with a cation-exchange resin, saturated with two different types of cations at different degree of saturation, against a third type of cation in solution have been studied by the equilibrium method. The exchange of the more replaceable ion has been found to be enhanced and that of the less replaceable ion suppressed; this interaction increases with the degree of saturation of the complementary ion. It has also been shown that the order of introduction of the ions in the resin during the preparation of the heteroionic resin salts has no influence on the release of the two ions. The variation of the selectivity coefficient for the ion, added against the two ions originally present in the resin, with their degrees of saturation has also been pointed out.

When an ion exchanger, saturated with two different types of ions, say A and B, is treated with a salt solution containing a third type of ion, C, the exchangeability of A and B is quite different from that when the exchanger in pure A-form or pure B-form is treated with the C-salt solution separately. This shows that one ion affects the exchangeability of another, and an ionic interaction exists in ion-exchange reactions. The earlier investigations were generally concerned with the relation between the degree of saturation of the exchanger with respect to a particular cation and its exchangeability mainly with heteroionic clays (Horner, *Missouri Agr. Expt. Sta. Res. Bull.*, 1936, No. 1 232; Marshall, *ibid.*, 1944, No. 1 385; Yarussov, *Pedology*, 1938, 6, 799; Mehlich and Colwell, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1943, 8, 179; *Soil Sci.*, 1946, 61, 369; Allaway, *ibid.*, 1945, 59, 207 et seq).

Weisz (Dessertation, Budapest, 1932), Yarussov (*Soil Sci.*, 1937, 43, 285) and Schachtschabel (*Koll. Beih.*, 1940, 51, 199) from their studies on ion exchange with heteroionic clay minerals conclude that the exchangeability of a cation decreases as the proportion of the complementary cation increases in the clay minerals. The same opinion is held by Jenny and Ayers (*Soil Sci.*, 1939, 48, 443). They have calculated on the basis of Jenny's (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1936, 40, 501) picture of the ion-exchange reaction that in a system of A-B-clay + C-salt, the exchangeability of A approaches zero as the proportion of B, the complementary ion, increases in proportion to A. They also found that the influence of the nature of this complementary cation, B, was highly significant. Thus, for instance, in the case of K-Ca, K-NH₄ and K-Na clays, the exchangeability of K⁺ at the same saturation in the different systems decreases in the order Ca > NH₄ < Na.

Bray (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 954) on the other hand held an essentially different opinion. He asserts that the exchangeability of a cation is not determined by its degree of saturation but by its own ability of release, and by the nature of the complementary cation. From replacement experiments with natural soils and HCl he obtained constants which he considered as a measure of the relative exchangeability of the cations.

Wiklander (*Ann. Roy. Agr. Coll., Sweden*, 1946, 14, 1) discussed these different view points and considered in some detail the influence of complementary ions in exchange reactions. On the basis of the law of mass action and the activity concept, he derived some equations for computing the release of ions saturating the exchanger. These equations are in fair agreement, at least qualitatively, with his experimental results. He showed that the percentage replacement of an ion was dependent partly on the nature of the ion, partly on the nature of the complementary ion, and

partly on the degree of saturation with the ions in question. The percentage replacement of an ion, say M, may increase, remain constant, or decrease as the degree of saturation with M is decreased. If the activity coefficient of M (f_m) is greater than that of the complementary ion, f_c , the percentage replacement of M increases; the latter remains unaltered if $f_m = f_c$, and decreases if $f_m < f_c$. If the saturating ions are dissimilar in valency, the one of lower valency is released in greater amounts, and that of the higher valency in smaller amounts as the degree of saturation decreases. Wiklander took different types of ion exchangers, e.g., clay, permutite and synthetic ion-exchange resins, both cationic and anionic, but in all his experiments he exchanged the saturating ions with very dilute HCl.

The exchangeability of an ion from a heteroionic exchanger depends also on the mode of preparation of the ion exchanger, as has been shown by Renold (*Koll. Beih.*, 1936, 43, 1), and Mukherjee (*Bull. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1942, 4, 1). This may be illustrated by the following experiment. A mixed K-Ca clay containing the same equivalent amounts of the two cations is prepared in one experiment by adding $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ first and then KOH, and in another experiment by adding KOH first and then $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. Exchange measurements of K^+ and Ca^{2+} against a third cation show that the amount of K^+ exchanged from the first heteroionic clay is greater than that from the second, whereas Ca^{2+} is exchanged in less amount from the first than from the second. Mukherjee (*ibid.*, 1944, 6, 19), and Ganguli and Mukherjee (*J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 56) have further shown that there are distinct critical ratios for the mono and bivalent cations at which these differences in exchangeability are observed. Thus, for instance, in a Na-K clay, the difference in exchangeability of Na^+ in the two clays, Na-K-clay and K-Na-clay, is not noticeable until the proportion of Na^+ in the clay exceeds 30%. The same is true of K^+ also. But for bivalent cations this critical proportion was found to be ($\sim$) 50%.

The present paper attempts to collect some more observations about the exchange reactions with heteroionic exchangers and mainly deals with the effect of the degree of saturation on the exchangeability of an ion from a cation-exchange synthetic resin, saturated with two different types of cations. As the symmetry values for different ions can suitably characterise the ion-exchange reactions (Jenny, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 2217), the ions were exchanged by a third cation added at its symmetry concentration, i.e., the amount of the cation added was always kept equivalent to the total amount of ions originally present in the resin. It was also examined whether the order of saturating the resin with the two cations had any effect on their exchangeability.

EXPERIMENTAL

"Zeo-Karb 225" was employed as the cation-exchange resin. The nature of the resin and the methods for its regeneration and purification have been described previously (Pochhali, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 451). For determining the total exchange capacity, a weighed quantity of the regenerated, air-dried resin was allowed to react with a standard alkali, added in excess, in a Jena glass bottle by shaking in a mechanical shaker for half an hour, and then the unchanged alkali was titrated against a standard acid. The amount of alkali consumed in reaction with the resin in its H-form gave the total exchange capacity expressed in m.e/g. of the air-dried resin.

The following different heteroionic resins were prepared:

The exchanger was saturated with the two kinds of ions at three different mutual degrees of saturation, e.g., 25-75, 50-50 and 75-25%. The actual experiment was arranged

in the following way: A weighed amount (~ 1 g.) of the H-form of the resin was taken in a Jena glass bottle. A calculated amount of the first cation was introduced into the resin by adding its hydroxide solution to the resin and keeping the mixture for 24 hours with occasional shaking. The second cation was then introduced similarly by adding the calculated amount of the corresponding hydroxide solution, so that the resin taken would now become completely saturated with the two cations added. The mixture was again kept for 24 hours with occasional shaking in a mechanical shaker. Then after decanting the clear supernatant liquid, which was almost neutral, the resin was partially dried in air in the bottle at room temperature. A second set of resin salts was prepared by reversing the order of introduction of the two cations. To distinguish between the two sets, these were represented in two different ways, e.g., A-B-R and B-A-R. As for example, $\text{NH}_4\text{-K-R}$ would mean the resin salt which was prepared by introducing K^+ first and then NH_4^+ , whereas $\text{K-NH}_4\text{-R}$ would represent the resin salt in which NH_4^+ was introduced first and then K^+ .

To the heteroionic resin salts in bottles were added NaCl solutions in such quantities as contained amounts of Na^+ exactly equivalent to the amounts of the total exchangeable cations present in the resins. The volume of the solution was always kept fixed at 50 c.c. The systems were then allowed to attain equilibrium on keeping for 24 hours with occasional shaking in a mechanical shaker. After equilibrium the clear solutions were analysed for estimation of the two cations replaced from the resins. The usual analytical methods were employed as described in an earlier publication (*loc. cit.*).

DISCUSSION

The results of the replacement experiments are presented graphically in Figs. 1, 2 and 3 for the

respectively. It is observed that the symmetry values of the different pure forms of the resin against a particular cation, e.g., Na^+ , are as shown in Table I.

FIG 1

TABLE I

Resin salt.	Symmetry value.	Resin salt.	Symmetry value.
NH ₄ -resin	48.0	Ca-resin	13.9
K-resin	41.0	Ba-resin	8.8

The order of ease of release for the different cations from their corresponding pure resin salts is: NH₄⁺ > K⁺ > Ca²⁺ > Ba²⁺.

Now, if we focus our attention to the percentage exchange of the ions from the mixed resins, it is found that the release of the ion having higher release capacity is enhanced and that of the ion having lower release capacity is suppressed. This interaction, e.g., the enhancement in the release of one ion at the expense of that of the second ion, is somewhat proportional to the ratio of their ease of release, i.e., their symmetry values. Thus the interaction is greatest in the case of Ca-NH₄ resin and least in the system K-NH₄ resin. On comparing the symmetry values the ratio of NH₄⁺ to Ca²⁺ is also found to be highest, being 48.0 : 13.9, but the ratio of those between NH₄⁺ and K⁺ is very small, being only 48.0 : 41.0. The ratio of the symmetry values of Ca²⁺ and Ba²⁺ (13.9 : 8.8) being intermediate between the above two, the interaction also lies in between them.

But though the release of one ion is enhanced and that of the other is suppressed, the total percentage of exchange from the resins with different degrees of saturation with respect to the two cations comes out to be purely additive; neither antagonism nor superadditivity is found as is evident from the straight line curves for the total exchange.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

From the percentage exchange of the two ions from the two different sets of the heteroionic resin salts, A-B-R and B-A-R, it becomes quite clear that unlike some clay minerals, the order of introduction of the two ions into the resin has no effect on their replacement. From both the series of mixed resins, A-B-R and B-A-R, the exchange of A⁺ or B⁺ from each of them is the same, within the experimental error, at the corresponding degrees of saturation. The effect observed in clay minerals is explained on the basis that all the exchange sites in them are not identical; some exchange sites are of higher binding energy than that of others. But here in the case

of this resin we may infer that all the exchange sites are identical ; there is no distinction between them with respect to binding energy.

FIG. 4

The variation in the percentage release of the two complementary ions with their degrees of saturation in the resin is shown in Fig. 4. Here the quantity of individual ion replaced has been calculated as the percentage of the amount of that particular ion present originally in the resin instead of that of the total amount of cations in the resin, as has been plotted in Figs. 1-3. It clearly shows how the replacement of a particular ion varies with its degree of saturation in the resin as well as on the nature of the complementary ion.

It is observed from the curves that in the system $K-NH_4-R$, the release of K^+ increases with its degree of saturation whereas the release of NH_4^+ decreases as its degree of saturation is increased. It is also seen that the replacement of NH_4^+ is enhanced and that of K^+ is suppressed in presence of the other, and this interaction increases with the degree of saturation of the complementary ion. In the system, $Ca-NH_4-R$, the relation between release and degree of saturation for Ca^{2+} and NH_4^+ is similar to that for K^+ and NH_4^+ except for the fact that the mutual interaction is far more intense, as is to be expected from the large difference between the symmetry values of Ca^{2+} and NH_4^+ . The replacement of Ca^{2+} is depressed to a large extent with increasing degree of saturation with NH_4^+ . But in the system $Ba-Ca-R$, the release of Ca^{2+} is enhanced instead of being depressed and that of Ba^{2+} is suppressed as Ca^{2+} is more replaceable than Ba^{2+} .

So it may be generalised that the release of the more replaceable ion is enhanced and that of the less replaceable ion is depressed in presence of the other, and this mutual interaction increases with the degree of saturation of the complementary ion.

How the selectivity coefficient of Na^+ against the other two ions present in the resin varies with their degrees of saturation is shown below. This selectivity coefficient can be represented as:

$$K_{A+B}^{\text{Na}} = \frac{\left[\frac{\text{Na}}{A+B} \right]_R}{\left[\frac{\text{Na}}{A+B} \right]_S}$$

where Na, A and B within parentheses represent the equivalents of Na^+ , A^+ and B^+ , the subscripts R and S indicating the resin and solution phase respectively. Here the concentration of the added Na^+ was always kept constant at the symmetry concentration. Hence the variation in the selectivity coefficient with the degree of saturation with respect to the two ions A and B present in the resin can be well compared. Since with the two series of resin salts, A-B-R and B-A-R, the values of the selectivity coefficients differ very slightly, the mean of the two values has been shown.

TABLE II

Values of K_{A+B}^{Na} .

Resin salt	A } B } R	Degree of saturation				
		A:	100	75	50	25
	B: }	0	25	50	75	100
	K } NH ₄ } -R	0.48	0.60	0.67	0.71	0.85
	Ca } NH ₄ } -R	0.026	0.078	0.21	0.41	0.85
	Ba } Ca } -R	0.009	0.014	0.020	0.025	0.026

From the data in Table II the values of the selectivity coefficient appear gradually to increase from pure A-resin to pure B-resin with increasing degree of saturation with B, A and B being the less replaceable and more replaceable ion respectively within the heteroionic resin.

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